

Plectranthus fruticosus Spurflower

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 1.5 to 2 meters

Distribution:

Plectranthus fruticosus has a widespread distribution from Caledon in the Western Cape up to the Limpopo province. Its natural habitat is amongst large boulders and along the edge of wooded thickets where it grows in well-drained and humus-rich soils.

Importance:

The Spurflower is grown locally and internationally as a flowering ornamental plant.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 23.83 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 19.26 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.49 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.3% [Single: 78.1%, Duplicated: 21.2%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 15 538.85 kilobases

Contig number: 485

Sample Contributor contact details:

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